

WEED MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND ORGANIC/INORGANIC FERTILIZER TYPES EFFECTS ON BELL PEPPER (*CAPSICUM ANNUM* L.) PLANT GROWTH AND FRUIT YIELD

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(Received 30th October 2024; accepted 17th February 2025)

ABSTRACT. The organic and inorganic weed management practices and fertilizer types' effect on Bell pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.) plant growth and yield were evaluated in the field. The experiment was conducted at the Department of Crop Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka research farm. The experimental design had two factors, A and B, which were in a 3 x 5 factorial layout using a randomized complete block design (RCBD). Factor A was weed management practices comprising black polyethylene mulch (BM), weedy (WD), and manual weeding (WF). Factor B was fertilizer types comprising of cow dung (CD) at 20t/ha; pig dung (PD) at 20t/ha; poultry dung/manure (PM) at 20t/ha, Inorganic fertilizer NPK (15:15:15) at 150kg/ha, and control (O). The seeds were raised in a nursery bed and transplanted monthly to a field with already prepared beds. The seedlings were transplanted in 45 plots measuring 2.25 square meters with 40 cm by 40 cm spacing. Data were collected on 4 sample plants per plot at 2, 4, and 6 weeks after transplanting WAT). Plant growth and yield data and the population count of identified weeds in each plot were collected at 2, 4, and 6 weeks after transplanting (WAT). The study showed that weed management practices had a more significant effect on the plant growth and fruit yield, with the weed-free plot given the highest. The fertilizer types had no significant effect on the plant growth. However, the black polyethylene mulched plots had the least number of weed populations. In conclusion, the weed-free plot with inorganic NPK fertilizer that yielded higher fruit is thus recommended.

Keywords: *Bell pepper, fertility, plant growth, fruit yield*

INTRODUCTION

Bell Pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.), sometimes known as sweet pepper, is of the plant family Solanaceae [1]. This crop is an important seasonal crop grown in Nigeria, mostly by small-scale farmers, often in a rotation with other vegetables such as corn, fluted pumpkin, or onions. Bell pepper has been reported to contain alkaloids, capsinoids, responsible for the hot taste, and it is important for neurological effects in the pharmaceutical industry [2, 3]. This crop has also been noted to possess anti-allergenic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-carcinogenic properties and can reduce cancer risk [4, 3]. According to Juroszek and Tsai [5] and Soare et al. [6], this crop's fruits can supply the following nutrients to human diets: carotenoids, minerals such as calcium and iron, as well as vitamins A, C, and E. In Nigeria, bell pepper fruits can be eaten as raw salad or cooked to be consumed in stews or soups.

Despite the economic importance of the bell pepper crop in Nigeria, there are a lot of challenges facing its production by farmers. Rapid depletion of plant nutrients and low soil fertility status in smallholder farms is the fundamental cause of decline, constituting

a strong limitation to crop production. Thus, these plant nutrients must be replenished adequately to avert a decline in crop productivity, low fertility status, and organic matter. Hassan et al. [7] recommended combining organic and inorganic fertilizers to produce bell peppers. Adeniyani et al. [8] recommended using organic waste to supplement inorganic fertilizers. Ngwu [9] noted that this is possible due to their method of nutrient release and the nature of nutrients. Fertilizers are external inputs that can be in the form of organic and inorganic, and the use of inorganic fertilizers has not been helpful due to fertility improvement measures to provide nutrients steadily for growing crops in recent times. According to Ricker-Gilbert [10], inorganic fertilizers are usually not available for low-income farmers. Ngwu [9] and several other researchers [11, 12, and 13] noted that inorganic fertilizer improves the growth responses of various crops in the tropics. Organic manure (cow dung, poultry manure, and pig dung) can be used as an alternative and supplement, as they are readily available in the tropics and can compensate for inorganic fertilizer. They have high organic matter that supplies nutrients or retains nutrients in the soil, and their chemical composition shows that they contain more than one plant nutrient [14, 15]. Organic manures are bulky, and the cost of transportation constrains their use, but they are good as they are needed in large quantities to satisfy the needs of crop nutrition [16, 17]. They release nutrients slowly and steadily activate microbial activity for nutrient release from organic matter decomposition [18], thus, they can sustain cropping systems through better nutrient cycling.

Another inherent defect of soil in the tropics, causing a low level of crop production of Bell pepper, is weed. Every seed requires space and other factors for growth and development. Therefore, the number of weeding and the time of the weeding needed to achieve the optimum yield of Bell pepper. Finding the best weed practice is important, as some researchers have shown that the bell pepper crop is not a good weed competitor [19, 3]. This study was therefore designed to determine the effect of weed management practices and fertilizer types on the growth and yield of Bell pepper under natural rain-fed conditions in Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. The hypothesis examined in this work is that plant nutrient addition in the form of organic or inorganic, together with weed management practices, can potentially increase bell pepper productivity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The experiment was in an open field at the Department of Crop Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka research farm, during the 2022 cropping season. The site is characterized by a bimodal season, the first starts from April to September and mid-October, while the second starts from October to March. The area's annual rainfall is about 1600mm, and the climate is humid tropical. The area is located at a longitude of 6.9, a latitude of 7.4, and an altitude of 475 m above sea level.

Source of Experimental Material

Bell pepper seeds were bought from East-West Seed Nigeria International Company Ltd. Poultry manure, cow, and pig dung were obtained from the research farm of the Department of Animal Science, University of Nigeria. The inorganic fertilizer NPK 15:15:15 and black polyethylene for mulching were sourced locally from the markets within the study city location. The materials used were locally available ones, and the

fertilizer rates tried were the quantities usually used by farmers in the area for such vegetables.

Design of the experiment

The adopted experimental layout was a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The treatments used were 3 methods of weed management practice (weed free, black polyethylene mulch and weedy control) and five types of fertilizer (control, poultry manure at 20t/ha, cow dung at 20t/ha and pig dung at 20t/ha and inorganic NPK fertilizer (15:15:15) at 150kg/ha) combined to form 15 treatment combinations and replicated three times to form forty five plot.

Cultural Operations

Nursery operations and sowing of seeds

The bell pepper seeds were raised on beds with only topsoil. On August 3rd, 2022, the seeds were sown by drilling to a depth of about 2-3cm between rows on a bed. Emergence was observed on August 8th, 2022 (6 days after sowing). The seedlings were watered every morning and evening for weeks before transplanting into the field.

Land preparation /treatment allocation

An area of land measuring 30 m × 7 m (210 m²) in length and width was used for the experiment. The field was cleared of grasses and mapped out using measuring tape and pegs. The field was divided into 45 plots measuring 2.25 square meters (1.5 m×1.5 m) with a 0.5 m pathway. The cleared site was divided into 3 blocks (representing three replications). Each replication contained fifteen (15) plots, giving a total of 45 plots in the experiment. Organic manure was applied at the rate of 20 tons/ha. On the 30th of August 2022, before transplanting, the mulch material, black polyethylene, was applied on the surface of the plot receiving the treatments, respectively, on 5th September 2022. Seedlings were transplanted on the 6th of September. NPK was applied at the rate of 150kg/ha, two weeks after transplanting.

Weeding

Weeding was carried out manually using a hoe at regular intervals except for the weedy check plot, which had uncontrolled weed populations throughout the experiment. For hoe-weeded plots, it was weeded at 2 weekly intervals.

Data Collection

Weed parameters

Weed data were collected using a 0.5 m² quadrat. This was done to check the level of occurrence and reoccurrence of weeds on each plot. An assessment was made per plot. The quadrant was randomly thrown within a plot, and weeds within the quadrant were identified, counted, and clipped from the base. The clipped weed species were identified and classified. The weed parameters were collected thrice at 2, 4, and 6 weeks after transplanting (WAP). The collected fresh samples of weeds from each plot were weighed and dried in a drying oven for 48 hours at 80 °C, then the dry weight was taken and recorded. Weed dry weight: The Dry weight of the sample was taken every two weeks with a weighing scale. Percentage of weed control efficiency (WCE%): Done by calculating the dry matter to determine the magnitude of reduction of weeds due to the

employed control treatment. Using the formula by Kumar et al. [20] expressed as a percentage, Eqn.1.

$$\text{WCE\%} = \frac{\text{Unweeded/untreated dry weight of weeds} - \text{dry weight of treated plots weeds}}{\text{Dry weight of unweeded weeds in the unweeded control}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 1

-Other parameters

Plant height (cm): The plant height is the distance from the shoot/root system junction to the shoot apex. It was measured with a meter or tape rule.

Stem girth (G): The stem girth was measured using a pair of Vainer callipers and converted to girth by the following formula:

$$\text{Stem girth} = \text{Diameter (D)} \times \pi (22/7)$$

Eqn. 2

Number of leaves: The number of leaves was counted.

Weight of fruit: A sensitive weighing balance determined the weight of fruits harvested per plant.

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on all the data collected. The treatment means were significantly differentiated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference at a 5% probability level. The analysis was done using GenStat Discovery software®.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study showed that weed management practices and fertilizer types significantly affected the plant growth parameters at $p < 0.05$. The findings revealed that the bell pepper plants grown in the plots treated with poultry manure had bigger stem girths and produced the highest number of leaves, while the plots treated with pig dung had the tallest bell pepper plants. The weed management practices on the bell pepper plant stem girth of the period measured (Table 1). However, at weeks 4 and 6 WAT, the weed-free treatment gave the largest stem girth. In addition, the weed-free treatment had plants with significantly higher numbers of leaves, which were statistically similar to the weedy check plot, while the black mulch had plants with the fewest leaves (Table 2).

Table 1. Effects of weed management practices and fertilizer types on bell pepper plant stem girth

Treatment	Weeks after planting		
	2	4	6
Weed management practices			
BPM	0.2	0.36	1.1
Weed free	0.2	0.38	3.7
Weedy	0.2	0.34	0.4
Mean	0.2	0.36	1.7
F-LSD _(0.05)	ns	ns	ns
Fertilizer types			
Control	0.2	0.29	1.46
Cow dung	0.2	0.32	5.75
NPK	0.2	0.35	0.42
Pig dung	0.2	0.39	0.45
Poultry manure	0.2	0.43	0.44
Mean	0.2	0.36	1.71
F-LSD _(0.05)	Ns	0.059	ns

BPM: Black polyethylene mulch, ns: non-significant, WAT: weeks after transplanting.

Table 2. Effects of weed management practices and fertilizer types on the number of leaves per plant

Treatment	Weeks After Transplanting		
	2	4	6
Weed management practices			
BPM	8.7	32.78	63.08
Weed free	9.1	41.67	58.88
Weedy	10.0	40.53	66.03
Mean	9.3	38.33	62.67
F-LSD _(0.05)	ns	5.915	ns
Fertilizer types			
Control	8.2	30.75	49.86
Cow dung	8.6	33.44	62.67
NPK	9.9	37.86	64.61
Pig dung	8.4	43.53	67.69
Poultry manure	11.4	46.06	68.5
Mean	9.3	38.33	62.67
F-LSD _(0.05)	ns	5.972	ns

BPM: Black polyethylene mulch, ns: non-significant, WA: weeks after transplanting.

The weedy check plots also had the tallest plants, which were statistically similar to those treated with black polyethylene mulch, while the weed-free plots produced the shortest plants (Table 3). This result confirmed the ability of the organic fertilizer to improve bell pepper productivity, likely due to its reported tendency to increase fertility, thereby enhancing plant growth [21, 22]. Growing horticultural crops such as bell pepper using organic manure possesses only non-toxic natural chemicals and maintains better soil health, which supports the growth and development of horticultural crops. Hence, the works of Adeniyani et al. [8], Ngwu [9], and Cai et al. [23] confirm the report that the

application of manure supplies the required nutrients and improves crop quality and soil fertility.

Table 3. Effects of weed management practices and fertilizer types on the bell pepper plants' heights (cm)

Treatment	weeks after transplanting		
	2	4	6
Weed management practices			
BPM	10.7	11.29	11.89
Weed free	8.7	12.81	13.32
Weedy	11.1	13.68	13.50
Mean	10.2	12.59	12.91
F-LSD _(0.05)	1.76	1.473	1.152
Fertilizer types			
Control	9.3	10.96	12.25
Cow dung	9.6	12.62	13.26
NPK	11.3	12.04	12.15
Pig dung	9.8	13.88	13.64
Poultry manure	11.0	13.46	13.23
Mean	10.2	12.9	12.91
F-LSD _(0.05)	Ns	1.473	ns

BPM: Black polyethylene mulch, ns: non-significant.

Fruit yield of crops, according to reports, is the net result of various interactions such as the fertility of the growth medium, good weather conditions, absence of weed competition, and a large leaf area, among others [24, 25]. The predominant weed species in the experimental plots were primarily broadleaves and grasses. *Amaranthus retroflexus* and *Portulaca oleracea* were the most dominant broadleaf weeds, while *Mimosa pudica* was the most dominant among grasses (Table 4). In Table 5, the effect of weed management practices on weed population had a significant effect at $p < 0.05$ on populations of broadleaves, grasses, and sedges; it also affected the dry weight of weeds as well as the calculated weed control efficiency. The weedy check plot had significantly the highest number of broadleaves, grasses, and sedges, respectively. However, the weed-free treated plots exhibited significantly better weed control efficiency. The black polyethylene mulched plots had the least number of broadleaves. The highest fruit yield of the bell pepper was observed in the weed-free control plots. This result was mainly due to the minimum competition experienced by plants growing under these treatment conditions, which allowed for maximum utilization of available nutrients and other growth factors such as moisture and light. These growth factors can influence bell pepper growth and yield components [19, 3, and 26]. Furthermore, Figueroa et al. [19] reported that weed management in bell pepper production is necessary for minimizing yield loss because the crop does not possess the ability to tolerate weed competition. Observations show that the weedy check plots had plants with the least bell pepper fruit yield due to crop-weed competition for available nutrients and space. The highest number of weeds occurred in the weedy check plot, comprising broadleaf weeds, grasses, and sedges; conversely, the plants had the least when black polyethylene was used as mulch. This observation confirms that black polyethylene mulch is more effective in weed control, which aligns with the report of Paminto et al. [27] suggesting that darker surfaces have a better ability to absorb heat, thereby limiting complete absorption of sunlight.

Consequently, the heat generated by the black surface smolders weed seeds and seedlings [28].

Table 4. *Predominant weed species on the experimental plots*

Scientific name	Family	Occurrence		
		2 WAT	4 WAT	6 WAT
Broad leaves				
<i>Amaranthus retroflexu</i>	Amaranthaceae	++	+++	++
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Portulacaceae	++	+++	++
<i>Ambrosia arlemisiifola</i>	Asteraceae	+	++	+
<i>Ficus carica</i>	Moraceae	+	++	-
<i>Heterotis rotundifolia</i>	Melastomataceae	+	++	-
<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	Malvaceae	-	+	-
Grasses				
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Fabaceae	++	+++	++
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	Poaceae	+	++	+
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Poaceae	+	++	+
<i>Penniselum purperum</i>	Poaceae	+	++	+
<i>Andropogon gerardi</i>	Poaceae	+	++	+
Sedges				
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Cyperaceae	+	++	-

Note: +: low weed occurrence, ++: moderate weed occurrence, +++: high weed occurrence.

Table 5. *The effects of weed management practices on weed data at 2, 4, and 6 weeks after transplanting.*

Weed Management Practice	BL/0.5m ²	GRS/0.5m ²	SGS/0.5m ²	DW (g/0.5m ²)	WCE (%)
BPM	1.27	0.9	0.20	0.99	28.34
Weed free	2.53	0.80	0.07	0.68	39.12
Weedy	12.27	5.40	1.47	0.58	0.00
F-LSD _(0.05)	4.4	2.71	1.13	0.75	0.5

BL: Broad leaf, GRS: grasses, SGS: sedges, BPM: Black polyethylene, DW: Dry weed weight, WCE: Weed control efficiency.

CONCLUSION

This study observed that weeding at two weekly intervals had a significant effect on the growth and yield of bell pepper. Weeding enhanced growth and produced more bell pepper yield than other weed management practices. The organic fertilizers (poultry and pig dung) affected the plant growth. The highest bell pepper fruit yield was obtained in the weed-free and NPK fertilizer plot (Figure 1). Therefore, since Bell pepper is an economically important fruit vegetable crop that is often impaired by weeds as its presence affects bell pepper plants, the weed-free plots enhanced the growth, yield, and reduced interference from weeds. This research recommends weeding at two weekly intervals because it had a higher impact on the crop yield. Although Black polyethylene mulch is a good weed management method, it is not used extensively due to the high cost of material and labour costs for installation. Therefore, the use of organic mulching methods as explained in this work is recommended.

Fig. 1. The treatment interaction effect on the number of bell pepper fruits produced per plant
BPM: Black polyethylene mulch, PM: poultry manure.

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